

Reduced spin and precession rates for GAIA: Implications for astrometric accuracy and the analysis of periodic phenomena

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ABSTRACT. Reducing the GAIA spin rate (ω) and/or precession rate ($|\dot{\mathbf{z}}|$) may be desirable for a number of reasons, mainly as a means towards technical simplification and cost reduction. The possible reduction of these rates by a factor 2 compared with the Study Report baseline is here investigated. Evaluation criteria are (1) the basic astrometric accuracy for single stars; (2) the ability to detect periodic phenomena with periods down to 1 day; (3) the parallax accuracy when solving also for periodic terms; and (4) the ability to correctly identify a real periodic perturbation. While the global astrometric accuracy for single stars does not degrade much when reducing the spin and precession rates, the ability to analyse periodic phenomena suffers very severely if the precession rate is reduced. By contrast, reducing the spin rate causes only a moderate degradation. The conclusion is that the spin rate could be reduced with only a minor impact on performance, while a reduction of the precession rate is unacceptable. The impact of the spin rate on the analysis of periodic phenomena should however be assessed in a more general context.

1 Introduction

In SAG-LL-014 (*The scanning law for GAIA*), two conditions were derived that together guarantee good sky coverage, i.e. that any point on the sky will be scanned sufficiently often (in at least six distinct epochs per year) and with a geometry that allows good separation of the astrometric parameters after a few years of mission. The conditions can be summarized thus:

- The precession rate of the spin axis ($|\dot{\mathbf{z}}|$) should be approximately constant and at least $3.95^\circ \text{ day}^{-1}$ (for Sun/spin axis angle $\xi = 55^\circ$) to $4.15^\circ \text{ day}^{-1}$ (for $\xi = 45^\circ$); this rate equals the maximum transverse speed of a star in the field.
- The spin rate (ω) should be large enough that the stripe of sky covered by the field overlaps on successive spins. This condition can be written $|\dot{\mathbf{z}}| \times (360^\circ/\omega) \leq \phi$, where ϕ is the transverse angular field width.

Both conditions were satisfied for Hipparcos as well as for the baseline GAIA mission described in the Study Report, the second condition with some considerable margin (ω was ‘oversized’ by a factor $\simeq 1.8$ for Hipparcos and 1.33 for the GAIA baseline).

Up until now I have considered both of these conditions as essential for a good mission. E.g. in GAIA-LL-040 (*GAIA accuracy: Scaling considerations*), the second (scan overlap) condition was strongly recommended, while the first condition was considered so self-evident that it was not discussed at all.

In the on-going re-definition of the mission, the question has come up whether some or both of these conditions could be relaxed in order to gain simplicity and reduce cost. In particular, it has been argued (Frederic Safa, Astrium) that reducing the spin rate should have no first-order impact on mission accuracy, because the reduced number of transits on a given object would be exactly compensated by the increased integration time available in each transit. The same argument can be given for a reduced precession rate.

A main objection to this argument is that the smaller number of transits could make the temporal distribution of observations much less favourable e.g. for double star processing, orbital solutions and variability analysis. All of these are likely to lose from having the total integration time concentrated in a few epochs, rather than spread out over many epochs along the mission. This objection, however, is more based on intuition than actual numbers.

In an attempt to quantify the problem, the scanning and subsequent calculation of astrometric parameters have been simulated for a few simplified test cases. The main tools for this investigation are the programs `ns1.f` and `scan.f` described in SAG-LL-026. The first program computes the scanning law, which is then used by the second to simulate the scanning across arbitrary points. A lot of *ad hoc* modification had to be made especially in the second program.

2 General assumptions

All simulations were made for a Sun/spin axis angle of $\xi = 45^\circ$, but the qualitative results should not be sensitive to this assumption. Two Astro fields were assumed, with a basic angle of 108° (again, this value should not be critical) and a transverse field width of $\phi = 0.66^\circ$. A total mission length of 5 years was assumed, without interruptions.

Three cases of the scanning law are compared:

1. The *reference case* just satisfies the two conditions mentioned in the Introduction. Thus, the (mean) precession rate is $|\dot{\mathbf{z}}| = 4.15^\circ \text{ day}^{-1}$ (corresponding to $S = |\dot{\mathbf{z}}|/\dot{\lambda}_s = 4.209$), and the spin rate is $\omega = 96 \text{ arcsec s}^{-1}$. The angular standard error in the along-scan coordinate is $\sigma_\eta = 1$ per single field crossing (transit).
2. The case of *reduced spin rate* has the same precession rate as the reference case, but the spin rate is $\omega = 60 \text{ arcsec s}^{-1}$, or half the current baseline value. On account of the longer integration time per transit, the standard error per transit is $\sigma_\eta = 0.7906$.
3. The case of *reduced precession rate* has $|\dot{\mathbf{z}}| = 2.075^\circ \text{ day}^{-1}$ ($S = 2.1045$), but $\omega = 96 \text{ arcsec s}^{-1}$ and $\sigma_\eta = 1$.

In subsequent figures (except Fig. 3), the top, middle and bottom diagrams correspond respectively to these three cases.

TABLE 1. Sky averages, and the RMS variations over the sky, of the number of transits per star (N) and of the relative standard errors in the astrometric parameters.

Case	$ \dot{\mathbf{z}} $	ω	N	λ_*	β	π	μ_{λ^*}	μ_{β}
1	4.150	96	135.0 ± 43.4	0.147 ± 0.037	0.124 ± 0.011	0.182 ± 0.030	0.103 ± 0.026	0.089 ± 0.013
2	4.150	60	84.3 ± 27.2	0.148 ± 0.038	0.125 ± 0.012	0.183 ± 0.031	0.104 ± 0.027	0.089 ± 0.013
3	2.075	96	135.4 ± 48.8	0.150 ± 0.038	0.129 ± 0.016	0.192 ± 0.037	0.107 ± 0.028	0.090 ± 0.011

3 Astrometric accuracy for single stars

The scanning of 5000 stars randomly positioned on the sky was simulated, and the variances of the five astrometric parameters (in ecliptic coordinates) computed as described in SAG–LL–026. Sky-averaged results are given in Table 1, while the number of transits and standard error in parallax are plotted for individual stars in Figs. 1 and 2.¹

Globally, the astrometric accuracies are only marginally affected by reducing the spin and precession rates. However, individual stars can be affected much more, especially in the ecliptic region. The degradation factors for the individual stars are plotted in Fig. 3. Comparing Case 2 (reduced spin rate) with the reference case, the mean degradation factor in parallax is 1.007, the 90th percentile is 1.056 and the maximum factor 1.207. For Case 3, compared with the reference case, the mean degradation is 1.051, the 90th percentile 1.155, and the maximum 1.432.

The reduced precession rate gives an increased inhomogeneity of the accuracy, as can be seen in the bottom diagram of Fig. 3.

For the subsequent detailed analysis, three positions (‘stars’) were selected, below referred to as A, B and C. Their ecliptic latitudes are, respectively, $\beta \simeq -29^\circ$, $+14^\circ$, and -60° . Star A is located in one of the problem areas of Fig. 3 (bottom), while B and C are more typical cases at low and high ecliptic latitudes.

¹The corresponding diagrams for the baseline scanning law (using $\xi = 55^\circ$ and $\omega = 120$ arcsec s⁻¹) can be found in Figs. 2 and 3 of SAG–LL–026. Note however, that the ‘coefficients of improvement’ (COI) in SAG–LL–026 should be multiplied by $\sqrt{120/96} = 1.118$ to be comparable with the present results.

FIGURE 1. Number of transits for each of 5000 random positions on the sky. **Top:** reference case; **middle:** reduced spin rate; **bottom:** reduced precession rate.

FIGURE 2. Relative standard error in parallax for the 5000 random positions. **Top:** reference case; **middle:** reduced spin rate; **bottom:** reduced precession rate.

FIGURE 3. **Top:** degradation factor in parallax due to reduced spin rate, i.e. the ratio of standard errors for Case 2/Case 1; **middle:** degradation factor due to reduced precession rate (Case 3/Case 1); **bottom:** sky distribution of the positions with a more than 10 per cent degradation in Case 3.

4 Solutions including periodic terms

A significant fraction of all stars will require additional parameters to describe the motion accurately. The scanning must allow also these parameters (including the period) to be accurately determined, without too much impact e.g. on the parallax accuracy. It is not possible to consider here the very large set of possible alternative models, but I will take circular orbital motion as a representative example. Only periods from 1 day to slightly less than a year are considered. For any given frequency f , four new parameters are required, viz. the Thiele–Innes elements A , B , F and G (for $e = \omega = 0$) in

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta\lambda^* &= B \cos \Phi + G \sin \Phi \\ \Delta\beta &= A \cos \Phi + F \sin \Phi \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

where $\Phi = 2\pi ft$ is the orbital phase. Statistically, we have $(A^2 + B^2 + F^2 + G^2) = a^2(1 + \cos^2 i) \simeq (4/3)a^2$, where a is the semi-diameter of the photocentric orbit. Thus a can be roughly estimated as $\hat{a} = [(3/4)(A^2 + B^2 + F^2 + G^2)]^{1/2}$.

4.1 Detection of periodic perturbations

The ability to detect periodic variations in the position depends on how sensitive the solution of A , B , F , G is to random noise in the transits. If the along-scan coordinates have random errors with standard deviation σ_η , then the expected \hat{a} in the absence of any real periodicity is approximately given by

$$Q(f) = \left[\frac{3}{4} (\sigma_A^2 + \sigma_B^2 + \sigma_F^2 + \sigma_G^2) \right]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

This function was computed for the frequency interval² $f = 0.003$ to 1 day^{-1} in steps of 0.0001 day^{-1} . The resulting mean and maximum values are given in Table 2, and for star A the function is also plotted in Fig. 4.

The minimum detectable orbit at any given frequency should be a few times $Q(f)$. $\langle Q \rangle$ is therefore a measure of the detectability of astrometric binaries with known period. If the period is not known, but assumed to be in the above frequency range, then the minimum detectable orbit is a few times Q_{\max} .

4.2 Parallax degradation due to periodic terms

Assuming that a periodicity has been detected, and that the four additional parameters in Eq. (1) have to be introduced in the astrometric solution, we can ask how much this degrades the astrometric accuracy compared with the single-star solution. I quantify this

²The lower frequency limit was chosen in order to avoid the near-degeneracy at $f = 1/365.25$ with respect to the parallax, while lower frequencies are not expected to be problematic. On the other hand, frequencies above $\sim 1 \text{ day}^{-1}$ are unlikely in astrometric binaries. Finally, the step size was chosen to give adequate oversampling for a mission length of 5 years (Nyquist frequency $\sim 0.0003 \text{ day}^{-1}$).

TABLE 2. Mean and maximum values of the orbit detectability function $Q(f)$ in the frequency range $f = 0.003$ to 1 day^{-1} .

	Star A		Star B		Star C	
	$\langle Q \rangle$	Q_{\max}	$\langle Q \rangle$	Q_{\max}	$\langle Q \rangle$	Q_{\max}
Case 1	0.334	0.53	0.378	0.64	0.309	0.56
Case 2	0.343	0.56	0.402	0.69	0.307	0.56
Case 3	0.498	1.80	0.459	1.13	0.328	0.77

TABLE 3. Mean and maximum values of the parallax degradation ratio $R(f)$ in the frequency range $f = 0.003$ to 1 day^{-1} .

	Star A		Star B		Star C	
	$\langle R \rangle$	R_{\max}	$\langle R \rangle$	R_{\max}	$\langle R \rangle$	R_{\max}
Case 1	1.048	2.2	1.053	2.0	1.042	2.7
Case 2	1.052	2.2	1.058	1.9	1.044	2.7
Case 3	1.168	3.2	1.147	4.5	1.087	3.2

by means of the parallax degradation ratio

$$R(f) = \frac{\sigma_{\pi}(9 \text{ parameters})}{\sigma_{\pi}(5 \text{ parameters})} \quad (3)$$

For the same frequency range as before, the mean and maximum values of this ratio is given in Table 3. The function $R(f)$ is plotted for star A in Fig. 5. Note that this degradation factor comes on top of the single-star degradation factor discussed in Sect. 3.

4.3 Period identification (aliasing problem)

Assuming that there really exists a periodic perturbation with significant amplitude (well above the detection limits indicated by $Q(f)$), then we may ask whether the correct period can be identified in the data. To investigate this, I added a circular motion with amplitude $a = 10$ units and frequency $f = 0.03$ (or 0.1) day^{-1} to the noiseless observation equations for the three stars, and solved the orbital parameters in Eq. (1). This was done for all the frequencies in the range 0.003 to 1 day^{-1} . As expected, the resulting \hat{a} came out at the correct value (10) at the true frequency. Often, however, even larger values of \hat{a} appeared at quite other frequencies. (This is the well-known *aliasing problem* caused by insufficient sampling of the temporal domain.) Figure 5 shows the resulting functions $\hat{a}(f)$ for star A, when the true frequency is 0.03 day^{-1} . Table 4 shows the number of ‘false detections’ (with $\hat{a} \geq 10$) in the different cases.

TABLE 4. Number of falsely detected periods (with amplitude greater than the true value) in the frequency range $f = 0.003$ to 1 day^{-1} .

True $f =$	Star A		Star B		Star C	
	0.03	0.10	0.03	0.10	0.03	0.10
Case 1	0	4	23	4	0	0
Case 2	0	5	45	8	0	0
Case 3	71	150	200	137	10	4

5 Conclusions

Compared with the reference case ($\omega = 96 \text{ arcsec s}^{-1}$, $|\dot{\mathbf{z}}| = 4.15 \text{ deg day}^{-1}$), the reduced spin rate gives a very small increase in the overall astrometric errors for single stars (Table 1). The detection and analysis of orbital motion is degraded, but only by a few per cent (Tables 2 and 3); also the aliasing problem is almost unaffected (Table 4) in spite of the considerable reduction in the number of transits. This can be understood by looking at the actual distribution of *distinct* observation epochs, shown in Table 5 for star A: there are as many distinct epochs in Case 2 as in Case 1, only with fewer transits per epoch. In fact, at many epochs there is just a single field transit in Case 2, while in the reference case there is usually at least one transit in each Astro field. The large basic angle is beneficial here because it increases the chance that a star missed in one of the fields is picked up by the other. Clearly, however, the performance in Case 2 relies strongly on the assumption that no transits are lost due to dead time.

Reducing the precession rate also gives only a marginal impact on the mean astrometric accuracy of single stars, although the sky non-uniformity becomes significantly worse (Fig. 2). However, the analysis of the periodic phenomena is severely affected: the detection limit is sometimes increased by a factor 3 (Table 2), the astrometric degradation is of the order 10 to 20 per cent on top of the single-star degradation (Table 3), and the aliasing problem becomes very much worse.

In summary, a reduction of the spin rate appears acceptable, while a reduction of the precession rate is not. Nevertheless, further assessment of the reduced spin rate with respect to periodic phenomena would be needed to confirm this conclusion.

TABLE 5. Distribution of observation epochs for star A. T = approximate date of observation (days from the start of the mission); N = number of field transits clustered around T .

T	N (Case 1)	N (Case 2)	T	N (Case 3)
13	2	2	126	4
26	4	2	177	6
121	2	2	216	10
140	3	2	355	4
175	2	2	527	4
302	3	2	663	7
323	2	1	716	4
354	2	1	751	5
396	29	18	838	6
497	2	1	860	5
522	2	1	929	6
552	3	1	1061	4
678	2	2	1233	4
704	2	1	1461	4
730	2	2	1634	5
874	2	1	1768	6
903	2	2		
929	4	2		
1055	2	1		
1085	2	1		
1106	2	1		
1202	4	3		
1210	5	2		
1251	2	1		
1286	4	2		
1305	5	3		
1431	2	1		
1465	2	2		
1481	3	1		
1576	3	1		
1592	2	1		
1628	2	1		
1672	17	10		
1677	19	12		
1756	5	3		
1774	4	2		
1808	2	1		

FIGURE 4. Orbit detectability function $Q(f)$ for star A. **Top:** reference case (Case 1); **middle:** reduced spin rate (Case 2); **bottom:** reduced precession rate (Case 3). The minimum detectable orbit size is a few times $Q(f)$, expressed in the same unit as σ_η .

FIGURE 5. The parallax degradation ratio $R(f)$ for star A. **Top:** reference case (case 1); **middle:** reduced spin rate (Case 2); **bottom:** reduced precession rate (Case 3). $R(f)$ is the factor by which the parallax accuracy is degraded when periodic terms of frequency f are introduced in the solution.

FIGURE 8. The function $\hat{a}(f)$ showing aliasing for star A, if the true orbit is circular with amplitude 10 units and frequency $f = 0.03 \text{ day}^{-1}$. Higher peaks at other frequencies could lead to an erroneous identification of the orbital period. **Top:** reference case (Case 1); **middle:** reduced spin rate (Case 2); **bottom:** reduced precession rate (Case 3).